

A CRITICAL STUDY ON GRAMMAR LESSONS TEACHING METHODOLOGY AND THEIR PRACTICE ACTIVITIES AS IMPLEMENTED IN THE COMMUNICATIVE CLASSROOM

Bake Muhigwa Julien¹ⁱ

Balagizi Iragi Tchubira Samson

¹Assistant Lecturer of ELT,

Université Evangélique en Afrique,

UEA/ Bukavu, Democratic Republic of the Congo

²Assistant Lecturer,

UEA, Language Resource Center,

Democratic Republic of the Congo

Abstract:

Grammar lessons teaching methodology and their practice activities as implemented in the communicative classroom is the success of the teaching-learning process in which learners learning will result in a satisfactory school achievement. To achieve the goal, library research, observation, questionnaire and interview were used to collect theoretical and field data. The aim of the whole exercise was to investigate into how teachers of English at secondary schools handle grammar lessons and how they offer their practice activities, as far as communication is concerned. An analysis of the different preparation cards and field data revealed that Grammar lessons require sufficient practice activities and competence in the teaching of the English language so as to help learners to use language for communication. The findings led to some suggestions and recommendations in the sense of helping both learners and teachers to practice the language.

Keywords: grammar lessons; activities; communicative factors and linguistic practice

1. Introduction

The teaching of a given language, aims at helping the learners to use it for communication. The focus of this study is merely to put on communicative approach and principles which are the best ways used in order to allow learners to have communicative competence and skills. It has to investigate into how teachers of English at secondary schools handle grammar lessons and how they offer their practice

ⁱ Correspondence: email bakemuhigwa@gmail.com

activities, as far as communication is concerned. Through the above problem, the researcher is required to check the following:

- Do South Idjwi English teachers of fourth forms handle grammar lessons by emphasizing on communicative methodologies and learners' interactions in the language learning effective communication?
- Do they elaborate practice activities which are relevant to learners real life situation, in link with the objective designed while dealing with grammar lessons?
- What is the matter with their practice activities?

Learners still have difficulties in both communication and reception of English message thanks to: The teacher's carelessness of how grammar lessons should be taught by insisting on relevant approach which promotes learners' communicative approaches. Learners are not gratified with enough time to interact and practice the language during grammar lesson transformation. The provided practice activities are not linked to the lesson objectives although the successfulness of any lesson is signified by the practice activities in link with the objectives and teacher's facilitation with his/her communicative methodologies.

2. Methodology

This article is carried out by means of revealing out the approaches and methods through which teachers of English have to handle grammar lessons, with regard to communicative interactions. To reach the objective, three methods have been applied such as library research by selecting books, theses, articles and other related sources that allowed the researcher to be aware of the review of existing literature on grammar teaching lessons.

The researcher has resorted to the interview of some teachers and learners of some South Idjwi secondary schools. During interview research, he tried to put some oral questions to learners. He firstly asked teachers why their learners are not able to communicate in the target language although they learn the language for that purpose. Most of teachers assumed that their learners do not like English. A great number of pupils feel disappointed of English when it is taught to them. On the part of the pupils, they dislike English simply because they catch nothing; hence, it is somehow hard to like something that is difficult to understand.

The researcher has used classroom attendance so as to find out enough information which helped him to deal with different aspects found in the study. He has attended grammar lessons at Kashofu, Ziwa-kivu, Nyamusiru and Umoja secondary schools i.e. two lessons per each school. The data were collected on the basis of the preparation cards in different fourth forms of those schools.

The researcher has focused on communicative methodology and approach aspects of grammar lessons so as to improve teachers' ways of teaching grammar with the reference to learners' classroom interactions. This article will be helpful and contribute to the scientific world through the suggestions and pieces of advice, given in

side on how teachers of English ought to teach grammar lessons. Teachers will also get inspiration on handling grammar lessons by bearing in mind their learners' needs, that is, communication in the target language.

3. Review of Literature

Grammar is important since it is the language that makes it possible for the users to talk about the language. It stands for a number of words, word groups and rules that makes up sentences. Studying grammar, people learn how to analyze sentences, so that they can understand how their constituents gather (words, phrases, clauses) work together.

Reference [1] says that teaching grammar in a communicative way is important since it offers learners a new perspective which relates grammatical structure systematically, meaning, uses and situation. In this way, it helps learners to improve and extend the range of communicative skills in the language. Teaching grammar communicatively from the explicit interactions, but also to know why they exist as they help make the acquisition of the language less mechanical. Such as:

A. Group-work: Here, the teacher splits the class into small groups where learners react and interact freely among themselves as in genuine speech events. The teacher intervenes only when s/he is involved by learners or when he feels that it is good to do so. Example, after teaching reflexive pronouns; the teacher can give learners a task and tells them the following: Work in groups of five pupils per each, and then rewrite the following sentences by completing them with correct reflexive pronouns.

Use « *themselves, herself, himself, myself, and ourselves* »

1. *I crutch..... on the arm this evening (myself)*
2. *They fell down and hurt (themselves)*
3. *We loved so much that we thought of no one else (ourselves)*
4. *John is intelligent enough he trusts (himself)*
5. *Pupils cannot teach..... English or mathematics (themselves)*
6. *A woman should cook for her husband..... (herself)*

Each group must have a director, leading the activities. Reference [10] adds that "during group work activities the class should not be made up into more than six groups, each of these should have a leader coordinating the activities". The role of the teacher must be limited to giving instructions. After the group work activities one of the members of each group reports what they have judged as appropriate to the exercise given by the teacher. Here, the teacher involves other participants as far as the group work activity is concerned by the time of presentation. Group work is an important technique which teachers of grammar can insist on as it helps pupils to get one another's message through communication. It helps the teacher to address himself to the class as a unit. The same reference [10] says that "at the presentation and practice stages of learning, it is normally both economical and effective to teach the whole class as a single unit".

According to [2] pair group is divided into two sub-categories of group-work depending on the number of participants. This technique is used only when two learners exchange in the target language together; appear to specific duties which do not require more than two pupils only. For example, a duty requiring question and answer interaction.

Long and Porter suggests that: “small-group work in the language class room provides the optimum environment for negotiated comprehensible output. In fact, validity is claimed for group work on both pedagogical and psycho-linguistic group, quoted by [4]”. The language acquisition is received by the learners in a comprehensive manner throughout groups and in pedagogical arguments. Long and Porter suggested the importance of group work activities as follow:

Group work increases the opportunities for learners to use the language; improves the quality of students talk; allows greater potential for the individualization of instruction; promotes a positive effective climate; has been found to increase student motivation.

B. The question – free-response practice

This procedure consists of giving learners possibilities to use the target language in an individual way. The teacher puts to the whole class a question and a pupil having the answer responds. This technique has been referred to by some scholars of foreign language teaching such as [2], who says that it does not favour the involvement of all the pupils in the learning activities, which take place in the class room. Besides, it fits in the pre-communicative activities where the teacher is engaged in putting learners' questions one after another, to verify how well they are concentrated and encouraged in his teaching.

C. Guessing game

A technique which is mostly applied by beginners and may also be used to advanced learners. It allows pupils to use the language structures they have just acquired to express function in attempting activities, by the fact that these activities are games, then whoever pupil who guesses fairly is gratified and opportunities of communicative competence is developed.

According to [8] presents guessing game as bellow:

Student A: What am I doing? Student B: you are opening the door. Student A & B: We're writing at the black board. Teacher: what are they doing? Student C: they are writing on the black board. Student A&B: what are we doing? Student C: you're writing on the black board. Teacher: what were they doing? Student C: they were writing on the black board. Student A: Guess what I'm going to do next week (miming action). Student B: you're going to pack your suitcase. Student C: she is going to pack her suitcase.

Through mime the variety of the actions be expanded considerably and the activity becomes a competitive game with learners describing each movement and then guessing what is being mimed. This may be a total learner to learner practice in an individualized or group work program reference to [8].

D. Situational practice

It consists of exhibiting a situation to learners and requiring them to express their feelings, thoughts, agitation, emotions, and opinions... in relation with it. In such a situation, learners will thereby refer to the language structures they have learned. Reference [2] has suggested that the teacher should always resort to situations which interest the learners. If pupils lacked in situation, they could consequently not have much to say. This is the reason why teachers' skillfulness and creativity. Another reference [8] presents situation practice as below:

Teacher to A: where're you going terry? A: *I'm going to lunch* A to B: *would you like to come with us?* B: *fine.* B to C: *where will we go?* C: *let's go to the movies/cinema* C to D: *do you like movies/films?* D: *no, I prefer television.* D to E: *how old are you?* E: *I'm fourteen* E to F: *What about you?*

E. Self-directed dialogue

This technique consists of giving each learner a list of pieces of information to find out, [2] the list distributor turns on from learner to learner, in his group asking questions in order to provide the missing pieces of information. Here, every learner is given the opportunity to communicate in his group and after the collection of the information; the pupils may then be required to give a short report to the group in which he is a partner or the whole class, depending on whether all the class may profit from the learner's speech.

3.1 Principles of the communicative approach

Communicative approach was not only the contrast against structural approach but also its weaknesses such as language of formal correctness. There are many principles of communicative approach that cannot all be tackled in this section. Referring to [2] the following principles are mentioned here below:

3.1.1 Knowing what you are doing

This principle suggests that the pupils should constantly be aware of the function of the language forms they are learning. According to [2] states that it is psychologically gratifying if one can know what he can do with what he is learning. Learners must study to do things and perform actions. This is appropriate with the target language as in every day real life. Reference [3] writes that the teacher should look how to teach the function of the language forms. If he does so, he can just draw the specific aim which prompts him to teach the language in a correct manner. Learners must then perform the second language as in real life and know what they do.

Reference [4] argues that real life and psycho linguistically motivated pedagogic tasks seem to be both pedagogically and psycho linguistically sounds, but also appear to have a general support of the learners themselves. At the end of the lesson, pupils should be capable to respond questions like "what am I going to do?" And "why am I

learning to do it"? At the starting point of the lesson, learners should be aware of what they are learning to do. This may be of great interest in the lesson.

3.1.2 The whole is more important than the sum of its part

This principle concerns the way learners should be trained to operate with language units above words and sentences. As for [2] suggests the exercise activities on which teachers should focus, so as to have their learners practice the target language like:

Give the synonym of ..., Give the opposite of ..., Give the phonetic transcription of ..., Use ... in a sentence, Make a sentence with ...

Pupils feel engaged in the learning of the target language if only the language forms have to be practiced in life like context.

3.1.3 To learn it, do it

For [2] argues that the language forms that students learn should be relevant enough. The language forms should be taught in a genuine way to enable learners to use it for communicative real message. As a language, English should be taught in order to achieve the above purpose. To come closer to it, the teachers will do their best to provide their learners with particular items, in order that they can become competent in communication and interaction. The learners are the main actors in the transmission of the lesson. According to [2] asserts that learning should be the responsibility of the learners rather than the teacher's. He keeps in saying that the teacher is a helper, a facilitator of the learning and not a dominant figure who inhibits the learner's initiative.

3.1.4 Mistakes are not always a mistake

Since the teacher's aim is to advance communication rather than formal accuracy, he should therefore tolerate mistakes which do not interfere with communication, so as to promote the acquisition and not breaking it down. When communicating, it is good to verify whether the message conveyed is caught by the receiver. That is, the teacher, for despite errors, the utterance is supposed to be successful in case the latter do not break communication, as suggested by [3]. It stands for the sense that in the guess of getting the most appropriate language forms the learners may act grammatically or phonologically in correct language forms. In this situation he should not be seen as making mistakes if the message he is trying to convey is guessed.

4. Suggested Teaching Methodologies and Their Practice Activities

It looks into how these should be connected to the practice activities as far as language for communication aim is concerned.

The researcher will refer back to the way he criticized those methodologies and how they should be practiced in the second language acquisition. To do so, he has firstly turned to school after school where he attended and watched how teachers handled grammar lessons as far as teaching methodology and their practice activities are concerned. He has given the overall suggestions for Grammar teaching

methodologies and practice activities. The researcher has insisted much on techniques and strategies that a teacher of English may consider at most, while dealing with grammar lessons, for the communication increasing.

4.1 Preparation Card N°1 (Data Collected at Umoja Secondary School)

A. Suggested teaching methodology and practice activities

In the teacher's teaching methodology it has been observed that the teacher insisted in defining concepts and also emphasized on putting oral questions to pupils.

To make this method more communicative, the teacher should have started the lesson with pre-communicative activities. In such activities the teacher isolates specific elements of knowledge or skill which compose communicative ability and equip pupils with opportunities to practice them separately. The pupils are thus being trained in the part-skills of communication rather than practicing the total skill to be learnt. Reference [11] asserts that the aim of pre-communicative activities is the learners to practice using acceptable language with reasonable fluency, without being concerned 'to communicate meanings effectively'. To provide learners with communicative proficiency, the teacher should apply the classroom organization technique. It requires some class-activities as mentioned below:

"Identifying one picture from a set: A: has the set, B: has just one of the pictures. A: has to discover which one, B: is holding. *Discovering sequences or locations*: A: has a particular sequence of picture, and B: has to arrange his in the same sequence. *Discovering missing information*: two learners have an incomplete table and each has to get missing information from the other. *Discovering missing features*: one learner has a picture, and his partner has the same with features missing; the learner with the complete picture has to discover missing information...[11]."

B. Suggested practice activities

As mentioned in the preparation card n°1, the teacher has given the practice activities by asking oral question and also required the learners to make sentences using some of the studied pronouns: he, herself, myself, ourselves.

To make this application more communicative, the teacher should give learners exercises which emphasize on communicative aspects and principles, which must be arranged in interactive form. As [8] suggests that these exercises should be organized in the way that the teacher should talk to the learner and the learner to the others as follows:

T: I'm a teacher. I'm a teacher of English

T: Who are you? S: I'm Olive. I'm a student

T: Where are from? S: I'm from Costa Rica

T: What is your name? S: It's Olive, S1: Is your friend from Iran? S2: No, he is from Iraq. He's studying English

S3: Is Indira studying English too? S2: No, she's studying Economics. She's from India.

S4: Are your parents teachers too?

S2: No, they are not, they are farmers. S5: Who help them to cultivate?

S2: They always help themselves. We use to go to school.

4.2 Preparation Card N°2 (Data Collected at Umoja Secondary School)

A. Suggested teaching methodology

To introduce the lesson to the pupils, the teacher created a context as it is observed in the preparation of that lesson. After having created the context, he started writing items on the black board with which learners were required to make sentences. This method was not communicative as it could not help learners use the language in their real life situation and it could not help them interact.

Reference [8] argues that a course which prepares students to interact in specific roles in real life situations requires that the course designer “first discover what activities the job entails and what part is played in these activities by language of different kinds.

To make this context more communicative, the teacher should simply consider the class as that of dialogue as follows:

a)

T: Good morning class. P: good morning teacher.

T: How many are you in class today? P: Today we are twenty-five.

T: Are there any girls in our classroom. P: Yes, they are.

T: How many are they? P: They are five.

T: Are they all present? P: No, a few of them are present.

T: Are all those girls intelligent? P: No, only few are.

b)

T: What do you do after class? P: After class we go home.

T: Do you have much time to watch T.V? P: No, we simply have little time.

T: What about Sunday? P: On Sunday we have a little time to watch T.V because it is a day off. P1: Do you live in a big house? P2: Yes, because we have a little money.

P3: No, because we have little money.

c)

T: Do you have many books to read at your home? P: Yes, we have a few books.

T: Does Malu have chance to succeed? P: Yes, he has a little chance.

P1: Do you see students outside? P2: Yes, I see few students outside.

P2: Does Dove speak English? P3: Yes, he speaks a little English.

P3: Do you want any food after class? P4: Yes, I want a little food.

B. Suggested practice activity

After the teacher has created an accurate and meaningful context during the lesson teaching, he can then give the practice activities communicatively as below:

a) Make a group of four pupils, then think of the suitable qualifier ((a) little, (a) few, to complete the following sentences:

1) They live in a very small house because they have _____ money.

2) Very _____ can speak ten languages in the DRC.

3) This plant needs _____ water and it is very handy.

4) _____ pupils speak English very well in the Congolese schools

5) \$1 is _____ money to buy a phone

6) One spoon of sugar is _____ sugar to put in a cup of tea

Here, the task in group must be well stated by the teacher. It must be clarified to the extent that pupils help each other in the target language as [6] notes that group work must be well organized which means that the teacher must have made the task clear as well as who is working with whom and how for how long. In each group, a member will be taking notes and will give a short report at the end of the lesson.

4.3 Preparation Card N°3 (Data Collected at Kashofu Secondary School)

A. Suggested teaching methodology

The most techniques and methodologies applied by the teacher from the beginning up to the end of this lesson were the emphasis of language rules and structures. These language rules and structures were not used in the way that they could help learners be aware of why they are learning the language; that is, language for communication purposes. They could sound positive only if communicative behavior was put in advance. To draw the learners' attention, the teacher should refer to the contextual language teaching proposed by our investigation as following:

T: Morning class! P: Yes, morning teacher.

T: Today you are not numerous, why not? P: Because it has rained.

T: Why can you not come to school by bus? P: Because we sometimes miss transport.

T: What is the advantage of going to school by bus? P: The advantage of going to school by bus is to reach the school before time. If we go to school by bus, we cannot be late.

T: What can happen if you miss the bus? P: If we miss the bus, we can be late and the teacher can punish us.

T: Where are we? P: We are in the classroom.

T: Can you answer the phone rings in the classroom? P: No, if we answer the phone rings in the classroom, we can make noise and the teacher can chase us from the class.

a)

T: Have you ever arrived in Europe? P: No, but if we find money, after studies we will be there.

T: What will you do after your secondary studies? P: If we get state diploma, we will go to University.

T: If I were the president of the country, I could develop DRC. P: If I were a man, I could have much money.

P1: What would you have done if you had been a president?

P2: If I had been a president, I would have gratified studies for pupils.

B. Suggested practice exercises:

a) Fill in the blank spaces with the "if clause" in the following sentences:

- 1) I don't know the answer I'd tell you.
- 2) It wouldn't be nice you
- 3) I'm going to the concert
- 4) We can go to beach tomorrow
- 5) Do you mind..... the window?

b) Work in pairs and then make discussion about the correct if clause to fit in the above sentences.

4.4. Preparation Card N°4 (Data Collected at Kashofu Secondary School)

A. Suggested teaching methodology

To advance the learners' capacity in communication, the teacher should have dealt with class interaction techniques and /or demonstrative method. The latter helps the teacher to manage the class in the communicative perspective. For [6] adds that there is not better, or more explicit way to introduce new activities than for the teacher to demonstrate, or ask a group of students to demonstrate. The following communicative techniques should be applied by the teacher, so as to reach the target.

a)

T: Hi class. Cl: Hi teacher.

T: How are you? Cl: We are very well, thank you.

T: which language are you studying? Cl: We are studying the English language

T: Do you like it? Cl: Yes, we do.

T: How many are you today? Cl: We are twenty-five.

T: Is John present? Cl: Yes, he is.

b)

T: Which language do you prefer much, French or English?

P1: I prefer either French or English. P2: Which language do you speak when you talk to your parents? P3: When I am with my parents, I speak either Kiswahili or French.

P3: What do you do after class at home? P4: After class, I can either have a short rest or watch the T.V. P5: When we arrive at home, we can either help our mother to wash clothes or study in our copybooks. T: Are you a Christian? P: Yes, I am.

T: Which beer do you prefer the most, Martini or coca cola?

P: No one. T: So, you prefer neither Martini nor coca cola.

P1: Sarafina drinks neither juice nor Amstel beer P2: I am neither an American nor a Rwandan. P3: I like neither big girls nor slim ones. I am still young.

P4: I don't like to visit neither Rwanda nor Uganda.

B. Suggested practice activities

Work together in a group of four pupils and then find the right word to fill in the gap in the following sentences: "either or", "neither nor".

- a) She drinks beer juice, she simply drinks water.
- b) Kani's father is a waitertrader
- c) Bujuku is suffering from diabetes Cancer. He is healthy.
- d) Miss Lidia is American Indian. She is free in both countries.
- e) Tom said that he would contact me but he phoned write a letter.
- f) Sarah is Spanish Congolese. She is Ugandan.
- g) my father my mother comes at 7:00. They both come at eight.

4.5 Preparation Card N°5 (Data Collected At Ziwa-Kivu Secondary School)

A. Suggested teaching methodology

As it can be seen in the preparation card of this lesson, the teacher used the method of drawing lines during the teaching of this lesson. To make this method more accurate,

the teacher should have drawn a number of pictures on the blackboard having different sizes to accompany the underlined lines. Therefore, he should have proceeded as noted hereafter:

Make the comparison between Soki and James, box 1 and box 2 and between Sarah's result to that of Alice

a)

SOKI

JAMES

BOX1
1

=

BOX2
2

Sarah 9/10

House 1

Alice 9/10

House 2

Comment on the following pictures and situations.

Claude 7/10

Telephone

Alex 10/10

a copybook

Football 1

Football 2

Canoe 1

Canoe 2

b) Compare the marks (result) of these pupils
 Furaha 9/10, Elie 7/10, Salomon 7/10, Dove 8/10, John 5/10.

At this level, the teacher is considered as a simple guider and his task is to involve learners in the activity of comparing things drawn and the results of pupils on the blackboard, referring to adjectives.

B. Suggested practice activity

To internalize what the learners have acquired during the lesson handling, the teacher can avail some exercises for learners to resolve together as follow:

- a) Peter has got 5/10 and Paul either. - Peter is Paul.
- b) Both Nzamy and Bora are equally brown. Nzamy is Bora.
- c) Rwanda is DRC. (small)
- d) A cat is lion. (dangerous)
- e) Mathematics is than French. (difficult)
- f) A phone is than a car. (expensive)

Here the teacher requires the learners to work in group of 5. He then tells them to discuss the practice exercises before writing down the answers that they have judged relevant. Each group must have a group leader who will be guiding the group and will therefore point out a member who will give the result of their work in front of others.

4.6 Preparation Card N°6 (Data Collected at Ziwa-Kivu Secondary School)

A. Suggested teaching methodology

Like the suggested teaching methodology from the preparation card n°5, the teacher should have dealt with the techniques suggested by the researcher earlier. That is, he should have been drawing pictures on the blackboard. Then, should have asked learners to describe and find their differences using the degree of superiority. He should also have emphasized on conversation in the classroom and interaction between him and learners and learners to themselves as said earlier.

Examples:

- Compare two countries: the DRC and Rwanda according to their sizes and the way of living
- Compare these two lines (as persons):

In order to let pupils communicate, the teacher should have involved them in the classroom discussion. To do so, he could have put simple questions to his learners which are related to the use of the degree of superiority.

Firstly, he could have written some adjectives on the blackboard. For example: good, happy, lazy, and nice. After this stage, the teacher should have required the learners to observe those written adjectives and discuss how they can be used in sentences as degree of superiority.

P1: Before using these adjectives in sentences as degree of superiority, we must change them firstly as comparative of superiority as follows: good: better than; happy: happier than; lazy: lazier than; nice: nicer than.

T: Use these adjectives in sentences by respecting the structure

s+ to be + adj. + than + o

P2: Atulinda is lazier than Fadhili, she always fails.

P3: Joyce is nicer than Feza, she comes freshly from town.

P4: Living in town is better than living in the village.

B. Suggested practice activities

The teacher handled the practice activities by asking learners to complete the blank spaces by using comparison of adjectives of superiority. Focusing on the communicative methodology suggested by the researcher, the following practice activities should be more helpful to promote the communication. For instance, the teacher should have written a short meaningful dialogue on the blackboard which lacks the comparison of adjectives of superiority which has to be discussed and completed by learners themselves. Then, he should ask them to comment on it using the comparison of adjectives of superiority.

Example:

I saw my friend today whom we studied with at secondary school when he was (Thin) What I was. But today he has got (fat)..... What I am. When I asked him why is he getting fatter than what he was before at secondary school, he answered that he just lives in the town. He said, life in town is (Good) than that

of village. Finally, he said “if you go to town too, you will be..... (Happy) than living in the jungle. Everything is found in the town if you have money.

Each suggested answer by a learner should be discussed by the whole class to verify whether it is relevant.

4.7 Preparation Card N°7 (Data Collected at Nyamusiru Secondary School)

A. Suggested teaching methodology

In the preparation card of this lesson, the teacher insisted on the teaching of language structure rather than teaching the language structure for everyday language uses. To make this procedure communicative, the teacher should be creating contexts which engage the learners in the acquisition of the language in a genuine way. To come closer to this, the following contexts should be dealt with:

Example:

T: Hello class. **Cl:** Hello teacher. **T:** Do you like the English language? **Cl:** Yes, we do very much. **T:** I've got some questions to ask you today. **Cl:** What are those questions, please?

T: Ok, keep quiet and listen to them carefully and find answers. **T:** Do you know policemen?

Cl: Yes, we know them. **T:** How do policemen drive their cars? **Cl:** Policemen always drive their cars quickly. **T:** Who can compare policemen's way of driving a car to that of civil people? **Cl:** Policemen drive quickly a car, although civil people drive slowly.

1) **T:** Are you Christians?

P: Yes, we are. **T:** Do you know how to sing? **P:** Yes, we do. **T:** to whom do you sing?

P: We sing to God. **T:** What is your mood while singing? **P:** We always sing cheerfully, happily. **T:** Where are we? **P:** We are in the classroom. **T:** Do we have rude pupils in our classroom?

P: Yes we have. **T:** How do rude pupils answer to questions in classroom?

P: Sometimes rude pupils answer to questions impolitely.

B. Suggested practice activities

By the end of the lesson, the teacher asked some questions to pupils to check how well the materials are understood. These exercises consisted of filling in the gap and turn some adjectives into adverbs. This exercise can be relevant only when it is done in a communicative way. To make this exercise more communicative, the teacher should proceed as below:

a) The teacher should divide the class into small groups of 4 or 5 pupils. Then, pupils will be asked to say about how the adverbs of manner can be used in the exercise provided by him.

b) The model of exercise which should be provided should look like the following:

Work in groups and correct the following sentences by using adverbs of manner:

1) She is very old. She is walking (slow).

2) The boy is very hot. He is drinking (thirst).

3) The girl is very hungry. She is eating (hungry)

4) Children play (happy)

5) The goat is eating the man's beans. He is shouting (angry).

4.8 Preparation Card N°8 (Data Collected at Nyamusiru Secondary School)

A. Suggested teaching methodology

The teacher's method was simply based on language structure and rules without involving communicative approach which is the most helpful in the acquisition of the language for everyday usages. Reference [3] argues that the communicative approach remains the only way to get access in the real life because it frees interaction in socially acceptable manners so that learners learn the language as a natural part of life.

In order for the teacher to draw the specific purpose for which the language is taught, he should have proceeded as follows:

T: Asking silly questions, while studying is not good.

To teach: teaching English is a good career

To learn: P1: Learning English is good for pupils

To tell: T: telling bad story to the teacher is disappointed

To come: P2: coming late at school is penal

To see: P3: I enjoy seeing my uncle during the holiday

To read: P3: what about you Sarafina? Sarafina: reading book is what I prefer much during holiday

P4: dancing is my carrier. Is it the case for you? No, James?

James: playing football is mine.

P5: he enjoys sleeping every time.

P6: making noise in the class is not my habit.

P7: teaching is a good task.

P8: I like following recorded by [8].

Through these communicative approaches, learners will be likely to be engaged in the language learning in a normal way.

B. Suggested practice activities

The teacher has asked learners to complete verbs by their appropriate gerund, and then, he asked them to replace the verbs in brackets in gerund. So as to prevent learners from memorizing the language rules, the teacher should have stated the practice activities as follows:

Complete the following sentences using the verbs in () in gerund. Discuss the exercises in pairs:

- 1) Michael likes..... (Eat) in the afternoon.
- 2) (Steep) a lot is my everyday habit.
- 3) Does your job involve (Take) a lot of people?
- 4) He admitted (Drive) the car but (Try) demand it dangerously.
- 5) (Tell) lies is not good for Christians.
- 6) Bill is very good cook. Bill is very good at(Cook)

5. Recommendations

After having done investigation in some South Idjwi secondary schools, we found it better to make some recommendations which are in relation with the suggestions

mentioned earlier. These recommendations are relevant for whoever teacher who handles the language for everyday usage sake. The researcher would suggest English teachers the following:

1. The teachers should bear in their minds the purpose for which they teach the language, that is, communication.
2. They should be applying communicative methods in the language learning so as to adapt their learners to the second language acquisition.
3. Teachers are required to insist on communicative principles in order to achieve the language acquisition objective.
4. They are requested to plan the group work, pair work, classroom interactions and games which help learners to acquire the language in genuine way.
5. Teachers should not be emphasizing on language structures and rules while teaching, unless they are used to the extent of increasing learners' level of communication.
6. They must make sure that the objectives they create are related to the pupils' real life situation, which familiarize the learners with the language they are studying.
7. While handling the practice activities, the teachers should only provide practice exercises which are helpful in developing learners' communication skills.

6. Conclusion

This article has been concerned with a critical study on grammar lessons teaching methodology and their practice activities as implemented in the communicative class room. It has centered its focus on South Idjwi 4th form classes. The researcher has observed a number of grammar lessons and chosen only schools where teachers who are qualified in the English language teaching. Thanks to the direct observation, it has been remarked that 4th form learners in this area were unable to convey their messages and thoughts through communication in the target language. After investigating the causes and the origin of this incompetence in communication, the researcher noticed that those learners were not taught grammar lessons in helpful ways. That is, communicative ways by the fact that, the context through which their teachers handle the target language is not communicative. Learners are led to methodologies since the methodologies and practice activities provided by the teachers are not communicative. This can be well understood thanks to the lessons criticized in the present article in which the researcher presented the record of what the teachers dealt with, in the lessons attended. In fact, it has been observed that the techniques used by the teachers were not reliable at the extent that they were teaching about the language instead of teaching the language for practicing it. This can be explained throughout the lacks observed on the parts of the teachers, especially the fact of not insisting on the communicative approach, as it has been said previously. Indeed, the hypotheses suggested by the researcher match with this problem remarked on the side of the teachers. To resolve this problem, the researcher has availed a number of remedies to deal with, while handling grammar lessons. The researcher attempted to give helpful contexts and application exercises,

which the teacher should have resorted to in order to have their learners communicate easily in the target language. The researcher has collected then teachers' preparation cards which allowed him to tackle the critical view. The suggestions need to be taken into consideration by the teachers whose wish is to equip their learners with communicative skills.

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